

ENS SUI GENERIS

(sui generis being)

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Abstract: Physics reveals the strange truths of the Universe and suggests that we live in a cosmic solipsism, so we may discover that there is my universe and your universe. After finding that no factual state is repeatable, I discover a special moment in time, distinct from the past and the perceptible present or the future. Finally, I argue that the possibility of a personal universe, an unrepeatable cultural construct, can lead to an indeterminacy of reality.

Seth Lloyd, distinguished professor of quantum mechanical engineering at MIT, suggests that the Universe appears to have been licked off the salty rim of the primordial fire pit by the tongue of a gigantic cow.¹ In order to reach this astonishing conclusion, he considers the alternatives according to which the Universe would consist of all visible and invisible things—everything that is, was, and will be; or that it began 13.8 billion years ago through a gigantic explosion called the Big Bang and includes all planets, stars, galaxies, space, and time. Next to the claim that the Universe is a gigantic cow, Kafka seems like a modest neighborhood writer—and indeed so he appears when we approach the surrealism of quantum reality. Here reality itself has become distorted, turning into a mixture of dream and nightmare, where the rules of the game have changed without notice, exactly like in a painting by Dalí.

Adapting to the strange truths revealed by physics is far from easy, as we learn from science journalist Amanda Geffer.² She suggests that we may have to accept the idea that there exists my universe and there also exists your universe, but never something that we could call our universe. If there are multiple observers, the universe of any observer is just as valid as that of any other. More precisely, however, there exists only one universe at any given moment in time, and then we live in a cosmic solipsism. Reality would abruptly stop at the edge of each observer's frame of reference. Yet when we actually observe something, the superposition disappears and we are left with a single reality, extending only to the limits of the observational field.

This personal Universe cannot be named as *sui generis* in its genus, but can at best be designated by indicating its contents, as an observable interaction with an external nature accessible to the observer. What we have here is something with its own structure, rules, and internal logic, which entails an autonomous conceptualization inaccessible to third parties. Interactions within this universe are temporary and limited to relational contents, and the interaction of these contents gives rise to new contents without any determinate limit. At the point of contact with external nature as such, it will receive, each time, a sequential modification that can only institute its own validation. Through this encounter with nature, a new nature is born for the observer: we have the supernatural, we have the observer's personal Universe what the observer calls reality.

Reality appears at a precise moment of observation. A special moment of time, and, strangely enough to assert, the only possible time, although difficult to perceive. This time lies between past and present, immediately before the future. A moment of time that no clockmaker has yet accounted for: continuum time. The observed present will always already be past, and the future comes only for that which lives within the continuum. This special moment of time has

neither beginning nor end, just as being itself is found in neither. We may also say that the continuum has no memory of its own, for within it nothing has been and nothing will be; within it, being dwells. If I have not been understood, it is of no concern—we move on to matters that will further complicate this brief exposition.

Accepting that each person has their own perceptible universe within the continuum, there is something important that must be urgently added. Not in order to create even greater confusion, but to exit the situation into which we have just entered. We add the concept of the irrepeatability of any situation and here we are not speaking of a poem memorized by heart, but of one of the fundamental principles of modern physics: the No-Cloning Theorem.

In our everyday, macroscopic world, we can copy information without difficulty think of a photocopier or a digital file. At the subatomic level, however, the rules change drastically. According to quantum mechanics, one cannot create an identical copy of an unknown quantum state without altering the original state. This follows from the linearity of quantum mechanics. If we had a “cloning device” that works for one state and for another, when attempting to clone a superposition of those two states, the device would not produce two copies of the superposition, but rather generate an entangled combined state that is not a faithful clone.

This happens because any measurement destroys the existing state. In order to copy something, one must first “read” it and measure it. In quantum mechanics, the act of measurement collapses the wave function. Thus, the moment one tries to find out exactly what a particle is like in order to copy it, one changes it. The laws governing the evolution of quantum systems are unitary.

Although this appears as a limitation, the prohibition is in fact a blessing for security. It is the reason why quantum communications are (theoretically) impossible to intercept. If a hacker

attempts to “copy” the data traveling through a quantum optical fiber, the signal will inevitably be altered, and sender and receiver will immediately know that someone is eavesdropping. The same applies to quantum teleportation. We can “transfer” a quantum state from one place to another, but the original is always destroyed in the process. It is not multiplication, but transfer. You can have either the original or the copy, but never both simultaneously when dealing with a pure quantum state. These conclusions regarding cloning were independently reached by W. K. Wootters and collaborators, and by D. Dieks.³

If we draw a line up to this point, we find that it is possible for each person to have their own truly unique universe, and that nothing is repeatable. Following this same logic of irrepeatability, if I undertake an action, I will never find myself in the result of my action, for it will produce each time a result different from the one for which it was conceived, and I myself will be another as a consequence of the action just undertaken. Thus, it is futile for me to erect a statue in pursuit of immortality, because when the work is finished, I will no longer be the one from before the work, nor will the statue be what it was projected to be—although appearances may deceive. This potency, viewed as the modification through one’s own intention of something else seen as external to oneself and thereby as a continuation of what is one’s own beyond oneself, is a fiasco. If this is so, then the great struggle of contemporary humanity for patrimonial accumulation, as power over things within one’s power, is nonsensical.

Why mention all of the above? Because in doing so we have resolved the great desire of each of us—one we are ashamed even to acknowledge, believing we will never live to see it fulfilled: the problem of omnipotence. And yet the desire can be fulfilled, if we look where we must and when we must—toward the place and time in which world A unfolds. And let us not forget something else: if each person has their own irrepeatable universe, then we have

also resolved, on the other hand, the issue of immortality, for time, as phenomenal succession, is itself part of this universe.

The amelioration of the personal universe is a modification of culturality that is, of the place where we discover that something should be positioned among other things, according to what we have received or found as meanings. Thus my universe coincides with my culturality, with the way everything is arranged within me—or rather, with the way things are connected.

I observe that in the German intellectual tradition, culture is not understood as a mere collection of objects, traditions, or artistic products, but as a learned mode of relating to the world and to others, historically acquired and socially transmitted. This conception is linked to the classical German opposition between *Natur* and *Kultur*: what is natural is given biologically, while culture is the result of formation (*Bildung*) and learning. Immanuel Kant, in *On Pedagogy (Über Pädagogik)*, published in 1803, states that “Der Mensch ist das einzige Geschöpf, das erzogen werden muß”—man is the only creature that must be educated.⁴ Culture is thus the means by which human beings construct their relation to the world, and through which they construct both themselves and the world—they construct reality. A rudimentary form of culture also exists in animals, in the sense of learned behavior considered good to perform.⁵⁻⁶ Moreover, there is convincing evidence supporting natural epigenetic influence on phenotypic expression in terrestrial plants, although it is difficult to distinguish the epigenetic contribution.⁷

According to Wilhelm Dilthey,⁸ culture (*Kultur* or civilization) is the comprehensive system of interconnected totalities—families, communities, nations, or historical movements—in which the psychic structure (*Strukturzusammenhang*) of individuals creates unity and purpose, understood through lived experience (*Erlebnis*) and re-experience. This culture is

not reducible to general concepts but expresses individual historical realities fundamental to the *Geisteswissenschaften*, as opposed to the abstractions of the natural sciences.

This idea is taken up and systematized by Max Weber through the central concept of *Verstehen* (interpretive understanding). “Sociology,” Weber says, “is a science which concerns itself with the interpretive understanding of social action and thereby with a causal explanation of its course and consequences...”⁹ Through *Verstehen*, culture appears as a set of learned meanings that structure the way individuals interpret their own actions and those of others. Culture is therefore not an external “object” but an internalized mode of orientation in the world.

In classical cultural anthropology, compatible with the German tradition, culture is likewise defined as learned and transmitted, not innate. Edward B. Tylor famously defined culture as “that complex whole which includes knowledge, belief, art, morals, law, custom, and any other capabilities and habits acquired by man as a member of society.”¹⁰

For the German school, culture is a learned, historical, and interpretive mode of relating to reality and to others a framework of meanings that makes the world intelligible. There is no “neutral” access to reality, for humans always see, understand, and act through the culture they have learned. If culture is a mode of relating to reality and is learned, then it presents itself, or can be described, through language. If we assume that we have a private language, then we also have a private culture in which we are, fundamentally, our own educators. A so-called individual universe presupposes a private language of representation and manipulation, leading to a private culture of non-transmissible and irrepeatable elements, yet susceptible to conventional formulation. However, language as such primarily signifies public activity; it functions through rules understood by all, not through “labels” attached to

inner phantoms visible only to oneself, as suggested by Wittgenstein's "beetle in the box" from *Philosophical Investigations* (§293).¹¹

Since a private universe has been discovered—or may be interpreted as such—as a relation within a total-of-everything-that-is-for-me, we necessarily also have a private language: bricks of private culture that hold my world together but cannot hold another's. If we live inside this private universe, we may also become prisoners of it—prisoners of our own minds. This "privation of freedom" can be attributed only to the conceptual fragility of the ideologies that have filled our century and which raise serious questions regarding their viability. Culture constructed upon communally accepted language is a repeated attempt to ameliorate each person's universe, and it is humanity's most important achievement. This culture has also multiplied us; repetition and memory of what is well done explain our multiplicity and that of others—this is why we left Adam and the Garden of Eden behind.

It appears that we have an additional differentiation, a specifically cultural one, alongside the universal individual one. We thus live in different worlds, but our world is somewhat similar—never identical—to that of the community in which we were educated. Here I note the Sapir–Whorf hypothesis of linguistic relativity, which holds that language influences, or even determines, the way we perceive and think about the world. Thus: "Human beings do not live in the objective world alone..."¹²

If culture is a learned, historical, and interpretive mode of relating to everything else—meanings that make the world intelligible—and if the universe worthy of primary study is an individual one, communally correlated, then we must see how we can benefit from this cultural corpus. Culture is a corpus, not individual elements, which must be preserved in common. Preservation occurs through the establishment of connections, through the "binding" of mental objects distinct yet observable and functional only together with others.

A mental object may be designated but not described by a word, and a word cannot be defined except through the entire dictionary to which it belongs. Every word is a discursive relic, except content words, which indicate the place of the others.

A significant cultural corpus, as binding-together, is preserved and transmitted through religion. For St. Augustine, *religio* derives from *re-eligere*, to choose again. Later, in *Retractationes*, Augustine accepted the view of Lactantius, rejecting Cicero's *relegere*, and arguing instead for *re-ligare*—to bind again. This private universe, as the linkage among my mental objects, as a relation within a total-of-everything-that-is-for-me, thus appears as a plausible working hypothesis. We cannot speak of a new binding, since the author of the first binding is inaccessible to me, just as the private culture of any other person is inaccessible. What we can observe is only a re-binding: an optimization, for me, of what is accessible and already received as bound.

Binding into a total-of-everything-that-is-for-me is a reciprocal relation among mental objects, perfectible through an educational act. Re-binding is therefore a continuous rearrangement of the whole in search of the optimum. It is an act of culture as relation to everything else, learned and transmitted, not innate, yet one may indeed be an autodidact.

If we have a cosmic solipsism and therefore each of us has their own universe, then these universes will differ from one another, at least as historically hierarchized constructs. Each of us appears, from this perspective, as an individual universe containing everything necessary for its own establishment. This necessity is proven as interaction within it, proven as being alive, but ultimately at least in theory, it should also have its own purpose. But how could, and what would it mean for, a universe to have a purpose? In many such universes, the possibility does not arise, or if it does, no meaning is found in having a purpose. Perhaps a

purpose would be to look upon another like itself, in order to see itself, and if no such other exists, it will create one from itself.

Re-binding creates an *individuum est ineffabile*, a Latin expression capturing the essence of the ontological mystery of the human person, attributed to Thomas Aquinas, though rooted also in Boethius and Avicenna. The individual is ineffable: impossible to describe exhaustively through universal concepts or general language. Aquinas defines the individual as that which is indistinct in itself but distinct from others.¹³

These re-bound things, affirmed as belonging to another world, belong to the intellect—that is, to the private universe—but they exist, or rather, they are what primarily exists within this alterity of reality. Concerning social facts as expressions of the cultural factor, Émile Durkheim argues that they cannot be reduced to individual phenomena, but possess their own reality: a *sui generis* reality.¹⁴

A similar interpretation appears in Hans Kelsen's legal theory, where the legal system is conceived as a normative order irreducible to biology or psychology. Norms exist as “ought,” distinct from factual “is,” corresponding to the notion of a *sui generis* social reality.¹⁵

Plato, in *Republic* (507b–517b, among others), appears to be the first to formulate explicitly a dual ontology: a sensible, changing, material world accessible to the senses, and a world of ideas, intelligible, immutable, yet equally real.¹⁶

In a general philosophical sense, an object or domain of reality is *sui generis* when it cannot be reduced to or defined by reference to others, but has its own structure and rules. The Latin adage *sui generis* may be understood more essentially as a being that cannot be subsumed under a higher genus, that does not derive ontologically from another type of being. Here, *sui*

generis designates what is fundamentally unique—not through isolation or specific differentiation, but through the intimacy of its structure.

I have wished to use this concept here in a specific sense, none of us is repeatable, insofar as our being-in-the-world takes place primarily within that individual cultural universe mentioned above. More than that, none of us contains anything outside this personal universe—no external reference point to our being. From this perspective, and perhaps the only one that truly makes sense, everything is permanently possible for each of us. This fundamental arrangement in the world demands a paradigm shift: a move from an external universe accessible to quantification, to an internal universe inaccessible to others.

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